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APPLICATION OF BIMATRIX GAMES IN TWO-PARTY SYSTEM ELECTIONS

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Abstract

Game theory is a mathematical branch that explores decision-making approaches in situations of conflict. Elections are analyzed through “**collective choice theory**” as a game theory conflict. The relationship between the two main parties in an election is studied to produce a conflict model. This model is a noncooperative game where the players have finite sets of strategies and is therefore formed by a bimatrix game model. Several classical models, such as Prisoner's Dilemma, Chicken, and two-stage election games, are used as bimatrix games. These models are useful for making rational political decisions and addressing national security issues. The optimal strategies for players are determined through analysis of the games mentioned above. It is shown that the best decision for players in the first two models is to reach a compromise and not resort to election tampering. In the third model, the best choice is the equilibrium and the best situation is one where players do not engage in falsification from the beginning and only take revenge in response to falsification

Keywords: Bimatrix game, strategies, situation, payoff functions, optimal decision, Nash equilibrium situation, Pareto decision, revenge strategy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Game theory is a modern, rapidly developing field of the mathematical theory for receiving a decision [1,2,3]. From the point of view of a mathematical description under the receiving of the decision it is meant choosing of u element (strategy) from the definite U set. In this relation it is defined a rule of choosing and expediency of $u \in U$ element. The complete mathematical theory of receiving the optimal (rational, expedient) decisions in case of participation of several individuals (or party) is a „Game Theory“. The Theory of Games is defined as a mathematical theory of receiving the decisions in conditions of conflict. Contently (semantically) under „conflict we should mean such a phenomenon about which we can say, who and how does he participate in this phenomenon, what kind of results can have this phenomenon, who and how are interested in these results“. Thus, the Game Theory studies any form of social contradiction - differences of ideas, strategic (nonantagonistic and antagonistic), cooperation. In the Game Theory for all these forms there are labored out the mechanisms of fair solutions in conditions of the conflict i.e. the mechanisms of optimal solution [4,5].

Game theory is based on the premise that every player in a game has a clear preference for the outcome they desire. This means that they must be able to compare different outcomes and decide which one is the most advantageous. In order to make a choice from the available set of strategies, the player must analyze and evaluate the potential outcomes. The decision-making process is the foundation of game theory, and it is essential that the player selects the most optimal and rational choice. The goal of game theory is to study what it means to be optimal and to determine the principles behind making a fair and correct decision. Ultimately,

the player must strive to make a decision that is both expedient and beneficial.

The 1980s saw the establishment of **rational choice theory** as a cornerstone in socio-political sciences. In simple terms, rationality encompasses a person's ability to devise a strategy for their actions and interactions, aimed at attaining the most possible gains with the resources available to them, while taking into account the actions of their peers. Such choices are influenced heavily by the dynamics of one's interactions with others, as rational choices are made in scenarios where participants are mutually dependent, and where each individual's satisfaction is subject to the choices made by others.

When making a rational choice, sustainability should be considered. The principle of sustainable optimality is the Nash equilibrium principle, developed by John Nash in the 1950s. It states that in an equilibrium situation, changing the strategy of any player should not improve their situation [1]. This principle fundamentally changed **Adam Smith's “a man must act as he wills to succeed”** principle [3]. Unfortunately, many still make decisions based on individual or collective success rather than balance, **which leads to unsolved problems and affects quality of life**. The principle of equilibrium is the basis for the development of the theory of rational choice in neoclassical theory.

In this article, we mean that players use rational choice methods in a decision-making situation. We also mean that it will affect all levels of the sphere of rational politics: in elections - presidential, parliamentary, in parliament, in committees or in case of conflict and any difference of opinion between states.

2. THE GAME OF TWO MAIN PARTIES TO WIN THE ELECTIONS

It is imperative that we take action regarding the political tactics employed by the primary political parties during elections and the potential consequences that arise from such behavior. When we speak of national security, we refer to any circumstance that could put our country's integrity, our relationships with other nations, and our economy at risk. Therefore, any occurrence that endangers the security of the state must be handled promptly and efficiently.

The field of game theory examines elections through the lens of "collective choice theory". Here we note that according to this theory, in the case of objective voting and more than two alternatives, sometimes the winning alternative (candidate, law) may not be chosen, which is known as the paradox of voting [3].

The struggle for victory between two parties is not antagonistic. It is a strategic game in which each player has a finite number of strategies. Therefore, its model is a bimatrix game [6]. Let's say these parties {1,2} are players. Let us denote the sets of their strategies by S_1 and S_2 , respectively, and denote their payoff (utility) functions by H_1 and H_2 respectively, which are defined on the set of $S_1 \times S_2$ situations. Thus, our bimatrix game model is $\Gamma = \langle \{1,2\}, S_1, S_2, (H_1, H_2) \rangle$.

In the context of party games, we examine game theory well-known models frequently utilized to address political and national security issues [3,7].

2.1. G"PRISONER'S DILEMMA" GAME

The game in question centers around a scenario where two individuals are being separately interrogated by police officers. In this situation, if one of the suspects confesses to their alleged crimes and the other remains silent, the confessor will be granted their freedom while the other will receive a harsh penalty of 10 years in prison. However, if both suspects remain silent, they will be given a lesser sentence of only one year in prison. This game is often used to explore the complexities of decision-making and the potential consequences of one's actions. If both choose to testify, they could be sentenced to 8 years in prison. Each person has the choice to remain silent or speak. This situation can be related to elections. Assume that in the two-party game model, each player has two strategies: 1.N(no) - not to rig the election and 2.Y(yes) - to rig the election. For example, in the Prisoner's Dilemma model, the strategy "Shut up" means the legal action of the player - choosing the strategy N, and "Confession" - choosing the strategy Y. Therefore, in the model of the election game, both players have the same set of strategies - $S_1 = S_2 = \{1.N, 2.Y\}$. In the corresponding situations, we leave the payoffs of the players unchanged and write the bimatrix game:

$$(H_1, H_2) = \begin{array}{c|cc} & 1.N & 2.Y \\ \hline 1.N & (-1,-1) & (-10,0) \\ 2.Y & (0,-10) & (-8,-8) \end{array} \quad (1)$$

In (1) model, each player's action in the elections corresponds clearly to their utility. What are the optimal decisions for rational players in this game? In it, the only equilibrium situation exists only in pure strategies, that is (2,2) if both of them rig the election at the same time. (1,1) situation is optimal according to Pareto, i.e. non-falsification of elections is the best for both players. However, this situation is unsustainable. Whoever changes the decision will win. Therefore, a compromise must be made, which is similar to cooperation between two players. This means that neither side should rig the elections for their benefit. Instead, the decision that benefits both players should be made for the good of the country. Any other decision is less favorable. For this problem, the Pareto optimal (1,1) decision is opposite to the Nash equilibrium (2,2) situation.

2.2. "CHICKEN" GAME

It is a necessary model for analyzing conflicts of different ranges and for making political decisions. The content of the game has various interpretations, among which we cite the following: two vehicles are loaded with explosive weapons and their drivers compete with each other to pass a narrow road while driving in opposite directions. Both vehicles cannot pass each other while moving at the same time. The driver who first turns out of the way and gives way to another loses authority among his friends and is called a coward, while the other is considered a winner. If none of them deviate from the road, then their collision is inevitable, which will result in the explosion of cars and the death of the drivers.

To interpret this game in the language of elections, let's assume that both parties have the same set of strategies as in the first model - $S_1 = S_2 = \{1.N, 2.Y\}$.

Here we also have a 2×2 noncooperative bimatrix game. In the described game, giving up the road means N strategy, and continuing the road - Y strategy. The worst result - fraud (death of drivers) should be estimated by (-100). If neither player falsifies the elections (both drivers give way to each other at the same time), let's estimate their utility by 5. If one does not falsify, and the other falsifies the elections, then the utility of the first is (-10), and the utility of the second is 10. Thus, the game model has the form:

$$(H_1, H_2) = \begin{array}{c|cc} & 1.N & 2.Y \\ \hline 1.N & (5,5) & (-10,10) \\ 2.Y & (10,-10) & (-100,-100) \end{array} \quad (2)$$

In (2) model of the election game, we have two equilibrium situations in pure strategies - (2,1) and (1,2). This means that the optimal situation is when one rigs the elections, and the other does not. Here, there is also a single equilibrium situation in mixed strategies (18/19, 18/19), which means that each player's decision not to rig the election must be made with probability 18/19. In the given game, the Pareto optimal situation is (1,1), which corresponds to (5,5) payoffs, but it

is not sustainable. However, this situation - non-rigging of elections by both players is best for both.

2.3. GAME of "TWO-STAGE ELECTIONS"

The election games discussed above are one-stage, which means that during the entire election period, the player chooses one of two possible decisions: either N , or Y . Now suppose that one of the players who has chosen a strategy N , has information that his opponent has chosen a strategy Y at the initial stage of the election. In this case, the player acting with a strategy N , can choose a revenge strategy R or a nonrevenge strategy $\bar{R}$.

This is where the second stage of the game begins. We assume that if both players choose a decision $\bar{R}$ in the initial stage of the election, then the election will continue in the second stage as well, since both players will be powerless to retaliate (which means entering into a crisis). Accordingly, for the player choosing N in the first stage, we can define two strategies for the second stage of the game, the use of which will depend on the decision made by his opponent in the first stage of the game. These strategies are: 1 - to choose a strategy R , if his opponent chose a strategy Y in the first stage (devil for a devil's share), and to choose a strategy $\bar{R}$, if his opponent chose a strategy in the first stage (an

eye for an eye); 2 - to choose a strategy regardless of the strategy chosen by his opponent in the first stage (unconditional cooperation).

These two strategies provide the player making the decision N in the first stage with a complete plan of action for each stage of the game. Their content is as follows: at the first stage, choose N and at the second R , what we mark with (N, R) ; At the first stage, choose N , over the second $\bar{R}$, i.e. Strategy $(N, \bar{R})$. Finally, these two strategies together (Y, Y) strategy determine the possible decisions of each player in the bimatrix election game Γ and therefore both players here have the same set of pure strategies: $S = \{(Y, Y), (N, R), (N, \bar{R})\}$.

We write down the received game model Γ in the form of a 3×3 bimatrix game, for which we need to determine the values of the players' utility functions for each situation, the number of which is 9. We denote the pairs of players' utility in the situation (i, j) by (u_{ij}, v_{ij}) . Therefore, our game model will look like this:

$$(H_1, H_2) = \begin{array}{c|ccc} & 1.(Y, Y) & 2.(N, R) & 3.(N, \bar{R}) \\ \hline 1.(Y, Y) & (u_{11}, v_{11}) & (u_{12}, v_{12}) & (u_{13}, v_{13}) \\ 2.(N, R) & (u_{21}, v_{21}) & (u_{22}, v_{22}) & (u_{23}, v_{23}) \\ 3.(N, \bar{R}) & (u_{31}, v_{31}) & (u_{32}, v_{32}) & (u_{33}, v_{33}) \end{array} \quad (3)$$

In (3) game, the four situations (2,2), (2,3), (3,2) and (3,3) are status quo situations, so the utility of each player is the same in them, and we write the utility pairs of the matrix with the following notation:

$$(H_1, H_2) = \begin{array}{c|ccc} & 1.(Y, Y) & 2.(N, R) & 3.(N, \bar{R}) \\ \hline 1.(Y, Y) & (a_1, b_1) & (a_2, b_2) & (a_3, b_3) \\ 2.(N, R) & (a_4, b_4) & (a, b) & (a, b) \\ 3.(N, \bar{R}) & (a_5, b_5) & (a, b) & (a, b) \end{array} \quad (4)$$

In order to specify the utility values of the players in the obtained game, it is natural to make the following three assumptions: 1 - each player prefers to win more than the status quo, i.e. $a_3 > a$, $b_3 > b$; 2 - Each player prefers the value of the status quo to the situational utility obtained by the other player's cheating, i.e.

$a > a_5, b > b_5$; 3 - Each player prefers the status quo to any of the three outcomes of cheating - $a > \max\{a_1, a_2, a_4\}$, $b > \max\{b_1, b_2, b_4\}$.

Let's consider a concrete example of the game Γ , when the players' utilities, taking into account the assumptions made above, have the form:

$$(H_1, H_2) = \begin{array}{c|ccc} & 1.(Y, Y) & 2.(N, R) & 3.(N, \bar{R}) \\ \hline 1.(Y, Y) & (1, 2)^* & (1, 2) & (5, 2)^* \\ 2.(N, R) & (0, 2) & (2, 3)^{**} & (2, 3) \\ 3.(N, \bar{R}) & (1, 4)^* & (2, 3) & (2, 3) \end{array} \quad (5)$$

The two-stage election game analysis involves finding a compromise that is both Pareto optimal and Nash equilibrium, enabling each player to threaten their opponent with revenge: if you make the decision to

cheat Y , then I make the decision (N, R) . Such a situation allows each player to threaten the opponent with revenge - if he decides to cheat, he will make a decision (N, R) . Both players will receive less utility than in a

stable situation according to Pareto if they falsify the elections. This removes any incentive to change strategies. (N, R) . A given (5) game may also have a mixed strategy equilibrium, but in this case, it will not be interesting.

3. CONCLUSION

This article delves into game theory and optimal decision-making in situations where interests conflict, particularly in the context of a two-party political system. Three classical bimatrix game models are employed to scrutinize election outcomes and identify the best strategies for the players.

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